

Factors Influencing Pay Settings in Europe

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“Convergent forces in the shape of globalization of markets, European legislation and common product standards have led to the emergence of remarkably similar operational requirements in management policies in various countries”

Mueller, F and Purcell, J (1992:p15-34)

Introduction

This paper will attempt to address the above quote by Mueller & Purcell in the context of International Human Resource Management (HRM), by discussing the paradigms of globalisation, European Legislation, common product standards, culture, pay and reward systems and recruitment in terms on how they have influenced international HRM management policies globally.

In today’s modern society, organisations, their structure, strategy, Human Resource Management policies and procedures, and thus workforce are becoming increasingly more complex environments in which to operate in due to the dynamic and increasingly changing environment in which they find themselves. Over the past thirty years, and especially the last fifteen, the effects of globalisation upon organisations have observed many rapidly transforming their HRM practices to remain competitive with global players in the production of products and services globally (Redman & Wilkinson, 2006, Contemporary Human Resource Management; pg 23). International trade, according to Gahan & Lakmal (2009, ‘What shapes an individual's work values? An integrated model of the relationship between work values, national culture and self-construal’ The International Journal of Human Resource Management. Vol. 20, Iss. 1; pg. 126) exceeded US\$10.5 trillion, with world trade in services estimated at approximately US\$2.4 trillion, and only set to increase.

Globally, the international marketplace consists of a growing population of 6.6 billion people which is expected to reach 10 billion by 2050 according to the latest projections prepared by the United Nations (Faugoo, 2009 'Globalisation and Its Influence on Strategic Human Resource Management, Competitive Advantage and Organisational Success'; International Review of Business Research Papers Vol. 5 No. 4 June pg. 123-133)

Consequently as global wealth increases, consumers actively seek choice, and thus competition intensifies as organisations compete for market share and a slice of consumer disposable income. The top 500 companies globally account for seventy percent of world trade and eighty percent of international investment, where total sales of multi-nationals are now in excess of world trade, providing them with a combined gross product of more than developing countries national economies (Lucas, Lupton, Mathieson 2006 Human Resource Management in an international context London: CIPD pg 10)

As a result international Human Resources Management across the globe has had to adapt similar operational requirements within its practices to remain competitive within the parameters of reward schemes and benefit packages, training and personal development and a 'fair' work environment.

Globalisation

The rise of globalisation and thus the emergence of Strategic Human Resource Management (discussed later), within International HRM have created an international organisational structure very different to one observed years ago. The emphasis upon international competition, an increasing number of women within the work-force, and a more 'mobile' and diverse employee in flexible work has initiated a change within organisational HRM practice (Arrowsmith & Sisson 1999, 'Pay and Working Time: Towards Organisation-Based Systems', British Journal of

Industrial Relations, pg 52). Today management teams are forced to question ‘Do we have the right staff to accomplish what we need to do?’ ‘Does our workforce possess adequate knowledge which enables them to help drive us forward internationally?’ ‘If not, where and how can

the organization acquire the necessary skills? “What does the HRM function need to do in order to help achieve these?” and “How can we elicit the best out of our workforce, and consequently engage them?”

Figure 2 Globalisation [www.businessandpolitics.org] (see bibliography)

Traditionally the dominant hierarchical organisational structure led by directive management prominent over the last two decades, has observed a global decline, in favour of a more flexible and ‘flat’ structure better suited to adapt to change within today’s dynamic business environment. The Resource Base View (RBV) methodology (Faugoo, 2009 ‘Globalisation and Its Influence on Strategic Human Resource Management, Competitive Advantage and Organisational Success’; pg 125- 130) supports the notion that employee knowledge, talent and ‘know-how’ are central sources to the success of organisational performance, where a new structure entitled the ‘Type 3 Company’ lends itself to the ‘workforce’ as ‘*the*’ most important asset of the organisation (Hollinshead & Leat 1997 Human Resource Management , An international and comparative perspective; pg 45) suggesting that employee involvement and engagement within everyday business decisions are key success factors in managerial HRM policies.

European Legislation

Using the example of pay setting within international HRM, it’s a complicated procedure where factors such as employee productivity, company budget, inflation

rate, economic growth, rates of unemployment / employment, and labour market supply and demand, influence how collective bargaining over pay is undertaken (Schuler & Jackson, 2000 'HRM and Its Link with Strategic Management', pg 30).

Within the EU a number of key factors influence international HRM strategies, where a countries level of 'collective bargaining' (where employees use authorised unions to represent them (Broughton, 2010 The Institute for Employment Studies Pay Setting and Pay trends across Europe' Institute for Employment Studies IES publications pg 14) play a role in the level of compensation offered to employees. In the UK company-level bargaining dominates HRM strategy meaning that there are fewer unions to represent workers, as opposed to the Scandinavian countries where sector level is common. Over the past fifteen years, governments have actively encouraged a shift towards company level, away from higher levels of bargaining.

In other EU countries (Finland, Ireland and Spain) it is the national level that sets the framework for bargaining. What is apparent is that bargaining in the new EU member states from Central and Eastern Europe is not as developed as in the 'EU-15' countries (Broughton, 2010 The Institute for Employment Studies Pay Setting and Pay trends across Europe' Institute for Employment Studies IES publications pg 14), due to the fact that employer and employee organisations are often not yet as well established i.e. Poland at a company level is hindered by a lack of trade union representation and many agreements are reported simply to adhere to legal provisions.

Within the EU over the past decade it can be seen that pay has increased significantly in conjunction with restructuring of economies and the productivity increases that have resulted from this; within Lithuania it is estimated that pay has increased at a rate of up to 20 per cent a year since the country joined the EU

(Broughton, 2010 'The Institute for Employment Studies Pay Setting and Pay trends across Europe' Institute for Employment Studies IES publications pg 15). In contrast to this some members of the EU Germany, Spain, Portugal and Belgium have exercised pay moderation in recent years in order to remain competitive with the other member's states, an action signalling that that globalisation exerts a considerable influence over HRM policy within the EU.

Pay setting within the EU still affords controversy when the issue turns to 'gender', where the wage gap between male and female still comes under scrutiny. A range of remedial actions have been undertaken in recent years to try to improve the situation, where in Scandinavian countries the issue of occupational segregation (defined by groups namely gender within different professions) remains a challenge for HRM practitioners. One particular course of action has been to campaign for a cross-sector minimum wage of €1,000 a month, which they believe would boost women's pay (Broughton, 2010 'The Institute for Employment Studies Pay Setting and Pay trends across Europe' Institute for Employment Studies IES publications pg 16)

Common Product Standards

Currently the increasing scope for production and services to be geographically dispersed raises important issues for international HRM practitioners. One such factor is the rising growth of outsourcing which happens due to globalisation, where standard products that are easily described and valued, offer 'lead' firms the motivation to externalise functions so that they are distanced from each other, resulting in fragmented relationships across borders and thus global value chains (Gereffi, Humphrey, and Sturgeon, 2005 'The Governance of Global Value Chains: Analytical Framework pg 78-104)

In contrast to this, increasingly, multinationals with growing geographical operations are opting to keep activities in-house when the products are customised and the information flow across countries is complex (Edwards, Kuruvilla 2005 'International HRM: National Business Systems, Organizational Politics and the International Division of Labour in MNCs' pg. 1-21). In this situation, more common in pharmaceuticals and automotive industries, cross-border co-ordination takes place through the hierarchy of the firm, where the importance of international integration follows the assumption that managers in multinationals have incentives to build internationally standard HR Policies which must balance this against the need to be sensitive to the specificities of the various locales in which they operate.

This 'global-local' tension is assumed, normally implicitly, to be one that all MNCs must grapple with (reference as above) where Edwards and Ferner (2002, 'The Renewed "American Challenge": A Review of Employment Practice in US Multinationals, pg 94-111) define this as "*the realization of synergies across countries*". These particular firms have a degree of commonality in their operations across countries, and because the realization of synergies involves managers situated at the company's head quarters influencing the nature of policies and practices at site level. For example, Marginson et al. (1995, from Edwards and Ferner as above) have shown that MNCs that are integrated across borders are those that most commonly develop international policies on employment practice.

Consequentially what is apparent from this study is that an organisation's internal structure such as its HRM function doesn't seem to play an especially prominent role in the standardisation of products and services. Rather, external converging forces such as globalisation and cultural diversity are the key drivers for initiating these changes, therefore this validates Muller & Purcell's quote that HRM policies

can remain relatively standardised from country to country without hindering organisational success.

Culture

An organisation's workplace culture defines how it executes its business, manages its workforce and fosters an environment unique to it, nurturing talent in an increasingly competitive arena. Comprised of a "*set of frequent unspoken expectations from both employees and senior management, their behavioural norms and organisational performance standards*" (Warr, 2008 Work Values: Some demographic and cultural correlates' Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology pg 751) organisational culture exerts a major influence over international HRM strategy and therefore the practices which fall underneath it.

Geert Hofstede's theory of 'four cultural dimensions' (1980, 1984 'Culture's Consequences: International Differences in Work-related Values' pg 70-74) draws on distinct groupings of traits within multi-cultural teams. The Power Distance Index (PDI) acknowledges that lesser powered individuals of an organisation accept that the power balance will be distributed unequally, a common cultural mindset especially prevalent in organisations within emerging market economies. Individualism versus Collectivism, representing how cohesive a society is where the former enjoys prominence in western society providing an organisational culture where rules are adhered to by employees in a 'fair' environment, in contrast to the latter where strong cohesive bonds through loyalty lay dominant over standardised human resources practices.

Masculinity (assertive and competitive) against Femininity influence (modest and caring) varies enormously throughout society and is heavily influenced by culture and tradition; international human resource management therefore, in this instance has to adapt to country specific cultural and religious beliefs to ensure best practice

within its HRM policies. Finally the Uncertainty Avoidance Index that addresses the extent, to which a society feels comfortable within unstructured and uncomfortable situations, ensures that within developed countries, to maximise workforce productivity the organisation must have in place clearly visible HRM structures. Consequently the work of Hofstede has proved instrumental for HRM personnel in terms of creating suitable reward structures and training schemes in line with the employees of an organisation.

Further, the rise of 'nuclear' families within modern society, and the desire for a more fulfilling work-life balance observe more employees seeking flexibility within their workplace, through personally choosing a balance enabling them to enjoy an active and busy personal life outside of their professional one (Edwards, Ferner, 2002 'The Renewed "American Challenge" A Review of Employment Practice in US Multinationals', Industrial Relations Journal, 33, 2, pg 94-111) Building upon Hofstedes cultural dimensions, the theory that 'one size fits all' is becoming increasingly void, where colour of skin, ethnicity, nationality, religion, age, status, and education become the only constants within a largely heterogeneous workforce. Consequently as a result, the motivational factors for today's workforce will vary considerably, as opposed to a relatively homogeneous one thirty years ago.

Pay and Reward systems

'Pay and Reward' systems have differed dramatically over time, dependent upon the needs and wants of both the organisation and the workforce, instead adapting to ones best placed to suit the requirements at both at any given particular time. Known as 'mimetic' (Pauuwe, 2004 taken from Kessler, Heron, Gagnon 2006 "The Fragmentation of Pay Determination in the British Civil Service, pg 12) particular pay and reward schemes have dominated certain eras within HRM, where 'time-based' pay for example (employees receiving the same pay expressed in fixed hours

and waged, or a fixed salary) has enjoyed prominent since the turn of the century, supporting the theory of Frederick Taylor “*a fair day’s wages for a fair days work*” (Taylor, Frederic 1998, *The Principles of Scientific Management*, pg 18).

International HRM functions nowadays create and implement pro-active strategies within its recruitment, selection and training programmes, offering the workforce carefully created reward schemes and incentivization packages, with the objective of driving and maintaining high motivation levels, enabling employees to meet business targets. Aligning international HRM strategy to the business goals of the organisation globally, do however encounter challenges based upon the unique external pressures faced by each country.

However current contemporary work observe findings which suggest that international organisations with reward systems linked to business strategy do consistently provide higher returns than those not intrinsically linked to it (Dickmann, Brewster, Sparrow 2008 *International Human Resource Management - A European perspective* pg 90) Further, work by Hollinshead and Leat (1997 *Human Resource Management An international and comparative perspective* pg 45) has concluded that those organisations using strategically performance related pay (PRP) systems consistently perform better based upon financial parameters of earnings per share (EPS), return on assets (ROA), profit per employee, and cash flow. Therefore it can be surmised that the outputs of an effective strategic reward system implemented by the HRM function are centred upon the financial profitability of an organisation, which in turn supports its competitive advantage within the business environment.

Unsurprisingly, trends over recent years have observed organisational compensation pay-outs rising sharply due to escalating benefit costs, where in 2009 British employers were estimated to have spent £970 million on employee benefits

(Beardwell, Holden, Claydon 2004 Human Resource Management a Contemporary Approach pg 13).

Recruitment

The recruitment element of international HRM is considered by (Vance 2006 Managing a global workforce; Challenges and opportunities in international human resource management) to be outside the scope of the function on a global scale due to the apparent differences inter country such as political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental factors. The most obvious in this context are legislative requirements specific to the laws governing the land, where often *“employees are selected in one country or another, and wherever the selection is undertaken, there are a range of conventions and legal requirements that have to be met that will fit within the legal framework of a country”* (Harris, Brewster, Sparrow 2007, International Human Resource Management pg 50)

Current work by the European Union is attempting to eliminate the differences inter country, but as noted above within the pay setting literature there still remains a largely disparate inequality amongst those countries for example within the European Union. According to Vance, 2006 Managing a global workforce; Challenges and opportunities in international human resource management pg 68) there is a misleading assumption that the social, class and cultural values underlying management ideas are or should be *'normal'* for every country. However Scandinavia for example exhibits occupational segregation, where there still remains a largely unequal male to female ratio; therefore it can be assumed that organisation's would focus on recruitment efforts favouring women.

One particular course of action has been to campaign for a cross-sector minimum wage of €1,000 a month, which they believe would boost women's pay

(Broughton, 2010 The Institute for Employment Studies Pay Setting and Pay trends across Europe' Institute for Employment Studies IES publications pg 15)

Conclusion

To conclude, this paper attempted to address the quote by Mueller & Purcell in the context of International Human Resource Management (HRM), by discussing the paradigms of globalisation, European Legislation, common product standards, culture, pay and reward systems and recruitment in terms on how they have influenced HRM management policies globally.

The rise of globalisation within International HRM strategies has created an international organisational structure very different to one observed years ago, where a flatter hierarchical system enables quicker dissemination of information. European legislation has meant that collective bargaining over pay-setting differs amongst countries, where in the UK company-level bargaining dominates HRM strategy as opposed to sector-level within the Scandinavian region. Currently the increasing scope for production and services to be geographically dispersed raises important issues for international HRM practitioners, such as the growth of outsourcing. Culturally the rise of nuclear families offers the notion that heterogeneous workforces are on the increase due to increasing diversity, which leads onto pay and reward systems uniquely tailored to an individual's preferences. Finally, the standardisation of recruitment procedures is an area being addressed by European Union, but as noted previously there still remains a largely disparate inequality amongst those countries in regards to recruitment and reward structures.

To surmise, international HRM *is* influenced by the converging factors as mentioned above, which possess the ability to seek standardised guidelines on a global level. However as each country presents its own unique set of political,

economic, social and legal challenges, HRM strategies need to be adopted which fit specifically to the country in question.

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